

ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN ENGAGED IN SPORTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14274450>

Abstract. *Grade physical development of children and adolescents, the influence of physical exercise on growth processes, body type characteristics and the state of the body's functional systems. To assess physical development, the following physical development indicators were studied and assessed: somatometric height, body mass (weight), body mass index (BMI) and chest circumference. Physical development was assessed according to the WHO growth and development standards, as well as the index method. The study involved 517 young athletes from the sports medicine department of the adolescent dispensary in Tashkent. In this regard, anthropometric measurements (weight, height, body mass index - BMI, chest circumference) were conducted among students aged 7-16 years involved in sports (swimming and rhythmic gymnastics) in a comparative aspect with children involved in physical education in a comprehensive school.*

Based on the obtained results, effective approaches to assessing physical fitness and physical development in rhythmic gymnastics and swimming have been identified . Swimming and rhythmic gymnastics help harmonize the growth and development of children. Thus, the percentage of girls whose height, body weight and BMI indicators correspond to WHO standards ranges from 92.8% for 11-year-old girls to 97.5% for 17-year-old girls. The most harmonious development was observed in girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics. A similar picture was noted in young swimmers. The implementation of the developed program for comprehensive assessment of physical development into practice involved in rhythmic gymnastics and swimming, made it possible to improve the quality of the organization of the training process, individualization of physical activity, monitoring and evaluation of the impact of these sports on the development and health of children.

Keywords: *anthropometric measurements, physical development, weight, height, body mass index BMI, chest circumference, swimming, rhythmic gymnastics, cyclic sports.*

Introduction. Today, measures aimed at preventing non-communicable diseases in children and adolescents from early childhood have become one of the important problems of medicine. Physical activity reduces the risk of developing arterial hypertension, overweight and obesity, helps to strengthen the mental and cognitive development of children, improves the quality of life and the level of well-being of the family. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), "...more than 80% of adolescents in the world are not physically active enough. In the process of physical education of children and their involvement in sports, the study of physical development is of great importance for assessing the health of those involved, since data on anthropometric indicators in ontogenesis allow us to judge growth and development, help solve issues of sports orientation and selection, regulate the nature, volume and intensity of physical activity. The dynamics of physical development of children and adolescents reflects the influence of physical exercises on growth processes, body type features and the state of the functional systems of the body.

Purpose of the study: Grade The physical development of children and adolescents reflects the influence of physical exercise on growth processes, body type characteristics and the state of the body's functional systems.

The results of testing athletes involved in cyclic sports and physical education are presented. The study involved 517 young athletes from the sports medicine department of the adolescent dispensary in Tashkent. In this regard, anthropometric measurements (weight, height, body mass index - BMI, chest circumference) were conducted among students aged 7-16 years involved in sports (swimming and rhythmic gymnastics) in a comparative aspect with children involved in physical education in a comprehensive school.

Materials and methods of the study. To assess physical development, the following physical development indicators were studied and assessed: somatometric height, body mass (weight), chest circumference, physiometric : lung excursion (inhalation, exhalation, pause), vital capacity of the lungs (VC), pulse rate, respiration, arterial pressure, muscle strength dynamometry. Physical development was assessed according to the WHO growth and development standards, as well as by the index method.

Results obtained. Based on the obtained results, effective approaches to assessing physical fitness and physical development in rhythmic gymnastics and swimming were identified .

Table 3.1.1

Indicators of physical development of girls involved in physical education in schools

Age, years	Body weight, kg	Height, sm	BWI, kg/m ²	OGK, cm
7	20.8±1.5	118.9±2.6	14.7±1.12	54.3±2.6
8	25.2±2.1	120.9±4.1	16.8±1.09	57.3±1.4
9	28.3±3.7	129.9 6.3	17.2±1.16	64.6±1.9
10	31.0±3.2	135.8±4.8	16.8±1.9	62.3±1.6
11	34.4±2.4	142.4±4.9	16.9±1.1	65.8±3.1
12	45.0±2.8	149.2±5.4	20.8±2.4	68.5±4.5
13	48.1±3.2	153.8±6.9	19.9±1.5	74.2±4.2
14	46.7±3.6	154.0±7.9	20.4±1.8	74.4±2.8
15	47.5±1.6	155.3±7.8	20.6±2.1	82±3.2
16	51.6±3.2	157.2±5.1	20.9±2.8	84.6±3.6
17	56.6±3.6	159.3±5.2	22.5±2.7	87.5±4.3

Table 3.1.2

Indicators of physical development of girls engaged in swimming

Age, years	Sports experience, years	Body weight, kg	Height, cm	BMI, kg/m ²	OGK, cm
6	0				
7	0	20.60±0.35	116.88±1.57	14.93±1.33	62.41±1.90
8	0	21.88±1.27	121.2±1.53	15.0±1.73	68.60±2.14
9	0.30 ± 0.01	28.00±1.98	134.86±2.81	15.6±1.70	70.50±2.14
10	0.42 ± 0.08	31.64±1.27	138.82±1.60	16.38±1.47	71.59±1.44

11	1.1 ± 0.02	34.99±1.83	142.38±2.14	17.2±1.48	72.14±1.01
12	2.25 ± 0.50	40.35±1.29	148.60±1.93	18.53±1.42	77.09±1.65
13	0.48 ± 0.06	44.18±1.70	158.94±2.26	18.12±1.44	78.44±2.02
14	1.10 ± 0.31	45.32±2.10	162.1±2.42	19.6±1.68	79.19±0.98
15	1.17 ± 0.34	46.89±1.27	163.2±1.18	19.11±1.49	80.65±1.44
16	1.24 ± 0.21	49.56±1.33	164.0±1.83	18.9±1.65	82.95±2.30
17	1.64 ± 0.32	55.3±3.2	166.7±5.2	19.3±1.7	84.7±2.2

Table 3.1.3

Indicators of physical development of girls practicing rhythmic gymnastics

Age, years	Sports experience, years	Body weight, kg	Height, cm	BMI, kg/m ²	OGK, cm
6					
7	1.3 ± 0.10	22.3±0.61	121.4±1.3	15.4±1.32	59.65 ±1.01
8	1.8 ± 0.15	24.4±0.77	126.6±1.7	14.9±1.3	62.52 ±1.97
9	1.8 ± 0.15	25.4±0.98	133.4±1.8	14.6±1.31	61.20 ±1.25
10	2.5 ± 0.26	27.5±1.4	137.2±3.2	15.2±1.59	61.54 ±1.45
11	3.5 ± 0.34	30.9±1.85	142.6±1.8	16.4±1.69	69.15 ±1.65
12	4.7 ± 0.41	34.2±1.79	148.9±1.7	16.7±1.21	64.37±1.09
13	3.4 ± 0.41	38.9±2.2	158.4±1.8	17.4±1.40	72.47±0.94
14	3.4 ± 0.41	40.6±1.9	161.4±1.5	17.9±1.69	73.56 ±1.65
15	2.9 ± 0.36	44.2±1.7	162.4±1.8	18.1±1.51	76.47±1.92
16	2.9 ± 0.36	46.5±1.4	163.8±1.9	18.0±1.64	79.19 ±0.98
17	3.2 ± 0.32	52.3±2.8	166.2±5.2	18.9±1.7	82.2±1.2

The analysis of anthropometric data was carried out in a comparative aspect with the standards of growth and development of children recommended by the World Health Organization.

The obtained anthropometric data show that the average indicators of body weight and height of girls involved in physical education in general education institutions relative to age in the comparative aspect in all age groups corresponded to the median indicators or were within the limits of "-1SD and the median" of standard indicators, which corresponds to normal indicators. A more pronounced difference is manifested in the height indicator of girls involved in sports.

Table 3.1.1. Body mass index of girls involved in sports compared to that of girls involved in physical education.

Comparative analysis shows that the average body mass index has its own characteristics. As can be seen from Fig. 3.1.1, the body mass of girls involved in physical education according to the school program up to the age of 11 has a multidirectional difference with the indicators of girls involved in sports depending on its type: at the age of 7, the body mass of girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics is higher, as they grow older and have more experience in sports, their body mass index is lower; from the age of 12, the difference increases and the body mass in this group is reliably lower than that of girls involved in swimming ($p < 0.05$) and physical education ($p < 0.05$). The opposite picture is observed in the growth dynamics. From the age of 12, the height of girls involved in sports is higher than the indicator of girls involved in physical education, the difference increases up to 18 years and is reliably higher ($p < 0.01$) (Fig. 3.1.2).

Table 3.1.2. Growth rate of girls involved physical culture compared to girls involved in physical education.

Table 3.1.3. BMI indicator of girls involved in sports compared to the indicator of girls involved in physical culture.

One of the indicators of harmonious development is the body mass index for age (BMI). According to the average indicator in all groups, BMI is within the standard WHO norms. Deviations in BMI with its decrease (below -1CD) indicate protein-energy malnutrition, the

pronounced degree of which (below -3CD) is assessed as exhaustion, with an increase in BMI (above 1CD) - about excess weight, the pronounced degree of which (above 3 CD) is assessed as obesity. Individual analysis revealed that there are deviations in this indicator towards a delay in protein-energy malnutrition in girls involved in physical education (2.1%); in girls involved in sports, these indicators were 0.6%. Overweight girls in the physical education group accounted for 1.5%.

Table 3.1.4. The GBC index in girls involved in sports compared to the index in girls involved in physical education.

The chest volume (CV) in all groups was within the normal range (Tables 3.1.1, 3.1.2, 3.1.3). As can be seen from Fig. 3.1.4, from the age of 9, CV is significantly lower in girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics compared to other groups ($p < 0.05$). Up to the age of 15, CV in girls involved in swimming is higher than in the comparison groups. And from the age of 15, in girls involved in physical education at school, CV reaches 87.5 ± 4.3 cm, which is 2.8 cm higher than in young swimmers ($p < 0.05$) and 5.3 cm higher than in girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics ($p < 0.01$).

Comparing these two sports, it should be noted that both had a beneficial effect on the development of girls, but the most harmonious development was seen in girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics.

Analysis of data obtained during anthropometric measurements in boys shows that body mass indicators of boys of all ages involved in swimming correspond to the zone of “-1SD – median” and “median and +1SD”.

Table 3.1.3

Indicators of physical development of boys involved in physical education at school

Age, years	Body weight, kg	Height, cm	BMI, kg/m ²	OGK, cm
7	21.83 ± 2.00	123.40 ± 0.42	14.34 ± 0.14	61.8 ± 2.2
8	24.86 ± 0.80	126.42 ± 1.22	15.33 ± 0.30	61.9 ± 2.2
9	26.52 ± 1.23	127.92 ± 3.56	16.1 ± 1.32	63.8 ± 2.7
10	29.50 ± 1.27	130.33 ± 1.76	17.32 ± 1.18	68 ± 2.9
11	33.22 ± 1.61	136.25 ± 1.73	17.51 ± 0.45	68.4 ± 3.3

12	36.03±1.42	140.61±1.68	18.72±0.58	70±4.1
13	39.60±1.54	144.34±2.25	19.04±1.72	73.2±3.8
14	40.39±1.55	146.05±1.35	18.53±1.64	76.5±4.7
15	49.92±2.49	155.75±2.64	20.18±0.68	79.7±6.6
16	53.43±1.87	160.57±1.91	21.08±0.56	80.7±5.3
17	59.23±2.31	168.73±2.03	21.01±0.64	83.7±2.2

A somewhat different picture is observed in the growth rates of boys involved in physical education according to the school program: the average growth rate of boys involved in sports aged 12 to 16 is within the range of "from -1CO to -2CO". Individual analysis showed that growth retardation was observed in 3.2% of cases in the group of boys involved in physical education, and among boys involved in sports, respectively, in 0.2%.

Table 3.1.4

Indicators of physical development of boys involved in swimming

Age, years	Sports experience	Weight, kg	Height, cm	BMI, kg/m ²	OGK, cm
6					
7	0.96±0.3	23.52 ±0.51	124.92 ±3.02	15.1±1.21	59.86 ±0.95
8	2.57±0.3	24.86 ±0.80	128.48±2.35	15.4±1.8	61.38 ±1.49
9	2.40±0.2	25.92 ±0.95	131.74±3.56	15.1±0.9	72.38 ±1.24
10	1.70±0.3	29.50 ±1.27	136.25 ±1.73	17.5±3.1	73.65±1.06
11	2.65±0.2	37.03±1.29	144.90±1.94	16.7±1.8	76.05±1.79
12	3.33±0.3	39.60 ±1.41	146.05±1.35	18.7±2.9	78.83±1.25
13	4.87±0.3	40.39±1.55	151.42±1.47	18.3±1.7	79.9±1.41
14	3.88±0.2	41.65±1.91	162.4±1.63	18.6±1.3	83.00±1.73.
15	4.85±0.3	51.92±2.49	167.21±1.7	18.6±1.6	86.1±1.69
16	5.5±0.32	60.00±1.73	172.33±1.65	19.7±1.6	88.43±1.29
17	5.8±0.31	64.5±1.56	177.7±1.86	19.3±1.54	90.6±2.9

Fig. 3.1.5. Body mass index of boys involved in swimming compared to those involved in physical education according to the school curriculum

Fig. 3.1.6. Growth rate of boys involved in swimming compared to for those involved in physical education according to the school curriculum.

The analysis of the harmonious physical development of boys by the BMI indicator showed that the average indicators in all groups did not show any lag behind the standard indicators corresponding to the median or "- 1SD and median" and "median and +1SD". At the same time, the average BMI indicator of boy athletes corresponded to a greater extent to the median of WHO standards.

Fig. 3.1.7 BMI index in boys involved in swimming compared to those involved in physical education according to the school curriculum

The chest volume (CV) in all groups corresponded to normal values and from 9 years of age was significantly higher in young swimmers ($p < 0.01$).

Other indicators of physical development also correlate with the data obtained. For example, protein-energy malnutrition of varying degrees was found among children involved in physical education to a greater extent than among boys involved in sports (only 1.8%). Excess weight among boys involved in physical education was 2.6%; and in the group of boys involved

in sports, not a single young athlete was overweight. In a comparative aspect, sports contributed to a more harmonious physical development of boys.

Fig. 3.1.7. The GBC index in boys involved in swimming compared to those involved in physical education according to the school program

Obtained results. The comparative analysis data also showed that anthropometric indicators depended on the duration of sports activities. Thus, before classes at the sports school, the physical development indicators of boys and girls corresponded to the WHO standards in 78.0% and 84.0% of cases, respectively; in 4.0% and 4.0% of cases - "-1SD and -2SD", isolated cases - below -2SD; in 8.0% and 12.0% of cases - "+1SD and +2SD", as well as isolated cases above +2SD in both groups. After 3 years of sports, the level of physical development in 12.0% of girls aged 6-10 years in the group corresponded to the range of "-1SD - median" and "median +1SD", which is 4.0% more often than before rhythmic gymnastics. In 80.0%, the physical development indicators fit into the range of normal indicators and in 8.0% in the range corresponding to low indicators. In 4.0% of girls aged 11-16 years, the level of physical development was in the high range, in 80.0% - in the normal range, and in 16.0% - in the low range. In this observation group, there was a tendency for the growth parameter to decrease in 12.0% of girls, while in the 1st group (6-10 years), an increase in the growth parameter was observed in 4.0% of athletes.

Conclusions. In the comparison group, the indicators of the level of physical development both before and after the study were more often located in the range of normal indicators (70.0% and 80.0%), which is 8.0% more than in the 1st and 2nd main observation groups. In 8.0% of girls, the indicators of the level of physical development corresponded to the 70-87 percentile, which is 8.0% less than in the previous three years, 4.0% less than in the 1st main group and 8.0% more than in the 2nd main observation group. It was noted that girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics were 3 times more likely to have a level of physical development above average than their peers who do not do sports. Girls who do not do rhythmic gymnastics are 2 times more likely to have a level of physical development below average, compared to girls who do. Before classes at the sports school, the number of girls with deviations in the harmony of physical development was 34.0% (according to outpatient cards) in the 1st observation group, 20.0% in the 2nd group and 46.0% in the comparison group. Such data are due mainly to excess body weight of the 1st degree (8.0%, 4.0% and 20.0%, respectively, $p < 0.05$) or its deficiency (8.0%, 12.0% and 0, respectively,

$p < 0.05$). After three years of regular sports activities, excess body weight was not recorded in the girls of the 1st and 2nd main observation groups. They more often had a moderate body weight deficiency (12.0% and 16.0%). While girls from the comparison group more often had excess body weight (24.0%) than its deficiency (4.0%, $p < 0.05$). Growth studies (cross-sectional and longitudinal) revealed that the overall increase in body height in children aged 11-16 in the comparison group was 18.5 cm; in group 1 - 12.0 cm, in group 2 - 16.0 cm. The greatest increase in height was in children aged 11-16, during puberty, when girls grow more in leaps and bounds, but given that sports activities in this type of sport slow down the increase in children's height, girls who do not play sports were taller than girls who do. Dosed physical activity affects the level of physical development. Girls who do gymnastics have a more harmonious pace of physical development than their peers who do not play sports, the disharmony of whose development is most often expressed in excess body weight. Swimming and rhythmic gymnastics contribute to the harmonization of children's growth and development. Thus, the percentage of girls whose height, body weight and BMI indicators correspond to WHO standards ranges from 92.8% for 11-year-old girls to 97.5% for 17-year-old girls. The most harmonious development was observed in girls involved in rhythmic gymnastics. A similar picture was noted in young swimmers. In the implementation of the developed program for comprehensive assessment of physical development into practice involved in rhythmic gymnastics and swimming, made it possible to improve the quality of the organization of the training process, individualization of physical activity, monitoring and evaluation of the impact of these sports on the development and health of children.

Summarizing the obtained data on physical development indicators, it can be said that sports activities contribute to the harmonization of growth and development of children of all ages, regardless of gender. The presence of children involved in sports, with protein-energy nutritional deficiency and excess weight, requires special attention to the organization of rational nutrition, which occupies one of the central places among other medical and biological aspects of training young athletes.

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